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Information technologies for predicting risks of digital heritage loss: an economic aspect

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***Abstract: Purpose.** The article is aimed at the analysis of the possibility to use the information technologies to predict and mitigate the risks of the loss of the digital heritage in Ukraine and its economical justification. This study aim at determining the major risk factors, assessing the cost-efficiency of the predictive tools and offer recommendations on enhancing institution and national strategies of digital preservation.*

***Methods.** The research uses both descriptive statistical analysis and econometric modeling as well as scenario forecasting. Cultural, educational and scientific institutions provided data to classify risk factors, whereas macroeconomic factors, including GDP growth and inflation, were included to determine how sensitive digital preservation activities are to external shocks. Regression and logit models made it possible to determine the extent of the relationship between institutional IT investment, the staff training, frequency of cyberattacks, and the*

likelihood of loss of digital heritage. The use of scenario simulation was employed to calculate the pessimistic, base, and optimistic estimates in the future of risks.

Results. The results showed that the most prevalent risk factors influencing digital heritage in Ukraine are financial instability, technological obsolescence, cyber threats and limited human resources. Those institutions that spend over ten percent of their budgets on information technologies proved to be far less vulnerable, and it proved the economic significance of the long-term investment. According to regression findings, every percentage point of increase of IT-related spending caused the likelihood of digital data loss to lower by 0.6 percentage points. The presence of macro economic instability, especially the negative growth of GDP, further heightened the chances of the heritage risks, which explains the importance of policy facilitation in the event of crisis situations. Predictive technology meant a lot: the institutions that employed machine learning and artificial intelligence applications enhanced their forecasting accuracy by 22% and saved costs associated with downtimes up to 1.7% of their annual budgets. Under optimal assumptions, scenario analysis showed that, even given very optimistic assumptions, the likelihood of large-scale loss of heritage would drop to 18 percent, as opposed to almost 50%, given very pessimistic conditions.

Conclusions. The findings illustrate that the issue of the loss of digital heritage in Ukraine does not fully originate in the technological sphere but also has a strong economic component. The rationality of distributing scarce resources, the strategic utilization of predictive information technologies and the concerted efforts on the part of the government and the institution are the necessary conditions of preservation. The identification of the major risks, the evaluation of economic determinants, and the analysis of predictive approaches have helped the research to achieve its objectives. Nonetheless, long-term cost-benefit analysis of predictive tools, prospects of international collaboration in the funding of preservation efforts, and the construction of region-specific strategies to fit to unequally distributed

infrastructure and conflict situations, still need to be studied further. The research provides unique findings since it connects technological fixes with economic research and will be of academic importance and also provide a working solution to policymakers and other authorities that must protect the digital heritage of Ukraine.

Keywords: *risk forecasting, cultural assets, digital economy, institutional resilience, investment efficiency, cybersecurity, econometric modeling, resource allocation.*

Інформаційні технології прогнозування ризиків втрати цифрової спадщини: економічний аспект

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Анотація: Мета. *У статті аналізуються можливості використання інформаційних технологій для прогнозування та зменшення ризиків втрати цифрової спадщини в Україні та його економічного обґрунтування. Це дослідження спрямоване на визначення основних факторів ризику, оцінку економічної ефективності прогностичних інструментів та надання рекомендацій щодо вдосконалення інституційних та національних стратегій цифрового збереження.*

Методи. *У дослідженні використовується як описовий статистичний аналіз, так і економетричне моделювання, а також сценарне прогнозування. Дані дані було взято з відкритих ресурсів з культурних, освітніх та наукових установ для класифікації факторів ризику, тоді як макроекономічні фактори, включаючи зростання ВВП та інфляцію, були включені для визначення*

чутливості діяльності зі збереження цифрової спадщини до зовнішніх потрясінь. Регресійні та логістичні моделі дозволили визначити ступінь зв'язку між інституційними інвестиціями в ІТ, навчанням персоналу, частотою кібератак та ймовірністю втрати цифрової спадщини. За допомогою сценарного моделювання було проведено розрахунки песимістичних, базових та оптимістичних оцінок ризиків у майбутньому.

Результати. Результати показали, що найпоширенішими факторами ризику, що впливають на цифрову спадщину в Україні, є фінансова нестабільність, технологічне старіння, кіберзагрози та обмежені людські ресурси. Ті установи, які витрачають понад десять відсотків своїх бюджетів на інформаційні технології, виявилися набагато менш вразливими, і це довело економічну значущість довгострокових інвестицій. Згідно з результатами регресійного аналізу, кожен процентний пункт збільшення витрат, пов'язаних з ІТ, призводив до зниження ймовірності втрати цифрових даних на 0,6%. Наявність макроекономічної нестабільності, особливо негативного зростання ВВП, ще більше підвищувала ймовірність ризиків, пов'язаних зі спадщиною, що пояснює важливість сприяння політиці у разі кризових ситуацій. Прогнозні технології мали велике значення: установи, які використовували програми машинного навчання та штучного інтелекту, підвищили точність прогнозування на 22% та заощадили витрати, пов'язані з простоями, до 1,7% своїх річних бюджетів. За оптимальних припущень сценарний аналіз показав, що навіть за дуже оптимістичних припущень ймовірність масштабної втрати спадщини знизиться до 18%, на відміну від майже 50 відсотків за дуже песимістичних умов.

Висновки. Результати дослідження ілюструють, що проблема втрати цифрової спадщини в Україні не повністю виникла в технологічній сфері, а також має сильну економічну складову. Раціональність розподілу обмежених ресурсів, стратегічне використання прогнозних інформаційних технологій та

узгоджені зусилля уряду та установи є необхідними умовами збереження. Визначення основних ризиків, оцінка економічних детермінант та аналіз прогнозних підходів допомогли дослідженню досягти його цілей. Тим не менш, довгостроковий аналіз витрат і вигод прогнозних інструментів, перспективи міжнародної співпраці у фінансуванні зусиль зі збереження та розробка регіонально-специфічних стратегій, що відповідають нерівномірно розподіленій інфраструктурі та конфліктним ситуаціям, все ще потребують подальшого вивчення. Дослідження надає унікальні висновки, оскільки воно поєднує технологічні рішення з економічними дослідженнями та матиме академічне значення, а також надасть робоче рішення для політиків та інших органів влади, які повинні захищати цифрову спадщину України.

Ключові слова: прогнозування ризиків, культурні активи, цифрова економіка, інституційна стійкість, ефективність інвестицій, кібербезпека, економетричне моделювання, розподіл ресурсів.

Problem statement in general form and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The conservation of digital heritage within the framework of global digitalization turns out to be one of the most acute problems of the contemporary era, especially to those countries that find themselves in the problematic economic and political environments [1]. The threat of the loss of digital heritage in Ukraine has reached a particularly acute level because of the combination of factors: constant war, numerous cyberattacks, lack of financial resources, and the unbalanced development of digital infrastructure. Simultaneously, the swift development of information technologies creates the new possibilities in forecasting risks as well as produces new risks connected with the technological obsolescence, the absence of standardization and the high price of providing the complex solutions. The issue that remains unsolved is the need to establish economically viable

solutions to foreseeing and addressing digital heritage risks that effectively incorporate limited financial capabilities and the true needs of Ukrainian institutions.

Generally speaking, the issue is comprised of the need to integrate two complementary activities: the creation of efficient information technologies to forecast the threats of the loss of digital heritage and the reasonableness of their future economic viability in the framework of the national context. On the one hand, digital heritage is a component of the national and scientific memory of society, the loss of which has irreparable consequences on the identity of the nation and the global reputation of the state. Conversely, the economic realities demand optimal ways of investing in such technologies to achieve the balance of the price of the solution and the level of risk mitigations it brings. Therefore, the scientific problem acquires a practical component, connecting the research to the formation of the effective state policy in the area of cultural, educational, and research institutions digital preservation, to the articulation of suggestions on the adoption of the modern risk management systems.

The overall research vectors are determined by the pre-existing relationship between the objective of the scientific problem and the practical activity. To begin with, the defining of the most important risks and factors that affect the likelihood of losing digital heritage. Second, the creation of economic models in order to estimate the viability of investments in predictive information technologies. Third, development of realistic suggestions to Ukrainian institutions, based on the experience of international experience and domestic limitations. The consideration of these objectives will lead to enhancing the scientific background of the field of digital economy and risk management, as well as serve as an effective tool in safeguarding the digital heritage of Ukraine in the changing and crisis circumstances.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The growing importance of digital transformation in cultural heritage has been identified as a source for both

preservation and sustainable development. Sandriester et al. refer to the fact that digitalization of heritage resources can contribute to regional resilience, especially in marginal regions, by opening new cultural and economic perspectives [1]. Their research highlights how technological change can safeguard heritage assets, and at the same time help drive wider socio-economic growth. This creates the link between digitalization of heritage and sustainable development, highlighting the dual role of technologies both in the preservation and in the regional economy.

At the same time, Pouloupoulos and Wallace call attention to the centrality of data in the design of the future of digital heritage [2]. They point out that management, integration and interpretation of data about cultural heritage critically determine how well societies are able to protect and reuse these resources. Their paper shows how the development of data-driven technologies shifts heritage institutions' approaches to risk, and in so doing, how technological infrastructures become connected to institutional decision-making processes.

The role of digital technologies becomes more crucial especially in the context of conflict, in which heritage is at great risk. Neglia et al. show how digital tools are irreplaceable tools for documenting, monitoring and protecting heritage in areas of armed conflicts [3]. This research is of particular relevance in the Ukrainian context, where war intensifies the risks of cultural and digital losses, underlining the urgency of the prediction and protection technologies.

On this basis, Mazzetto describes the promise of new technologies like digital twins in heritage building conservation [4]. By combining disciplinary processes, digital twins offer not only technical tools for preservation but also cost-effective risk management processes for the long term. The economic point is very obvious, in the sense that these tools avoid repeated physical action and enable institutions to simulate the risks before they occur and therefore forecast them.

In a complementary direction, Rababeh et al. suggest a framework for the use of digitized heritage technologies to improve user experience and understanding [5].

Their research emphasises the importance of digital heritage not being seen as a matter of preservation but also as an economic and cultural asset that can yield added value. This perspective strengthens the argument that investments in digital preservation need to be justified not only by protection but also by a role in enriching the society.

A more general description is provided by Mendoza et al., who performed an overview of preservation technologies with a systematic review [6]. Their research indicates considerable diversity in technological solutions but also identifies gaps in technology integration, standardization and economic evaluation. This corroborates the notion that while there are multiple solutions, they are not being implemented in a coherent manner nor with financial rationale and therefore institutions have fragmented approaches that are potentially inefficient.

The role of artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming more and more important in this context. Munster et al. suggest a research and development agenda for Europe that envisions AI as a game changing force in digital heritage innovation [7]. Their research indicates that AI can be used to optimize predictive models, automate inspection, and augment decision-making; but it also highlights the importance of cost and ethical considerations. This is particularly true for Ukraine, where budgets are constrained and AI adoption costs need to be carefully assessed against the economic benefits of its implementation.

Other advances are seen in Katifori et al, who discuss advanced technologies in digitization [8]. This article concludes that emerging methodologies will broaden the accuracy and availability of digital heritage and that they will at the same time introduce new challenges in terms of resource distribution and economic viability. Their study reveals the importance of finding a balance between innovation and sustainability, a tension that is at the heart of the economic dimension of the risk prediction challenge.

In addition, the concept of an "echo-based" heritage digital twin, which proposes to extend heritage building information modeling to dynamic, predictive systems, is introduced by Arsalan, et al. [9]. This trend is a move away from static digital records towards dynamic interactive platforms that evolve to changes and anticipate risks. The business case for them is that they can help minimize the long-term maintenance costs and optimize the use of resources.

Zhang et al. present the use of the explainable machine learning models for risk assessment of cultural heritage in China [10]. Their recent and seminal case study of the Ancient Tea Horse Road demonstrates the power of predictive algorithms to quantify risk while guaranteeing transparency and interpretability in the decision-making process. Their results give an example of how modern forecasting techniques can inform economic and institutional decisions especially in areas where resources are limited and trade-offs must be considered carefully.

Following the previous research, Slassi-Sennou and Elmouhib demonstrate that digital transformation mitigates financial and operational risk under two mediators: ICTs adoption and resistance to change [11]. Their evidence suggests that risk reduction is not a purely technological effect and is dependent on organizational uptake and behavioral dynamics. For Ukrainian heritage institutions, however, this indicates a double agenda: Implement predictive tools to prevent losses and work in parallel to invest in change management to overcome barriers to adoption that will otherwise negate the economic benefits of technology.

Stefani et al. support this view by suggesting an information security risk framework dedicated to digital transformation technologies [12]. Their framework combines asset identification, threat modelling, control selection and continuous monitoring. In a heritage context, this means mapping digital collections and preservation workflows as critical assets, matching controls with threat vectors (such as ransomware or integrity loss), and establishing telemetry for early warning signs. Economically, by reducing duplication of spending and misallocated controls, a

structured framework can help make cybersecurity a more cost-effective component of preservation budgets.

Leon et al. are concerned with fast and accurate digitization methods illustrated through several case studies [13]. Their contribution is directly relevant to risk prediction pipelines: precision capture, robust registration and completeness of metadata reduces downstream uncertainty in condition monitoring and anomaly detection. Increased capture fidelity reduces the chances of re-digitization and corrective work, which in tight Ukrainian budgets means real savings and better baseline for predictive models to identify deterioration or data loss hazards.

Naji et al. propose an integrated model of safety culture that boosts performance via the mediating effect of psychosocial hazards [14]. Although developed outside the heritage domain, the mechanism is instructive: Organizational climate influences human error, vigilance, and compliance. Applied to digital preservation, a pro-safety (risk-aware) culture - clear roles, non-punitive reporting, work load management - reduces process deviations (often the root cause of backup failures, mishandled migrations, unpatched systems). Thus, culture becomes a non-technical risk control to safeguard the return on technological investments.

Finally, Hodayoun provide macro level evidence that innovation and information technology increase financial resilience [15]. Their findings suggest that IT spending, if aligned strategically, protects institutions from shocks by making them more continuous and adaptable. For Ukraine, where conflict-fuelled volatility increases the likelihood of digital heritage loss, the priority given to innovative predictive tooling (e.g. explainable ML for incident prediction, automated integrity checks) is not only a technical upgrade, but a resilience approach that stabilises service delivery and preserves cultural assets under financial strain.

Taken as a whole, these studies show a consistent trend towards digital heritage preservation being more reliant on sophisticated technologies to not only preserve assets, but also drive economic and strategic decision-making processes.

The literature shows how the importance of predictive approaches - from digital twins to AI and machine learning - has grown in relation to heritage risks. At the same time, though, the unsolved challenge across most contributions is the economic justification of such technologies, in resource-constrained environments such as Ukraine, in particular. This gap highlights the necessity for research that combines the potential for technology with economic analysis to bridge the imperatives of preservation with sustainability of financial resources.

Identification of unresolved aspects of the general problem. Despite the fact that the issue of digital heritage conservation is well recognized in international studies, there are still many aspects that are not covered correctly, especially in the Ukrainian case. First, most present studies focus on the technological aspect of risk management and devote little attention to economic justification of investment in predictive information technologies. This creates a gap in the knowledge of how resource-limited institutions can rationally budget to optimize the protection of digital heritage.

Second, how to integrate the predictive models into wider national and institutional strategies has yet to be resolved. Although machine learning and artificial intelligence tools are proven to be very effective in predicting risks at the strategic level, their use in Ukraine is fragmented, with no way to standardize the process and systematically evaluate their cost-effectiveness.

Third, the relationship between macroeconomic instability and crisis conditions, and how these affect the sustainability of digital preservation systems has not been adequately researched. The current context of the war (including decreased GDP, inflation, and high cybersecurity threats in Ukraine) presents a specific context where digital heritage risks are further exacerbated. However, empirical models linking these macroeconomic variables to the probability that digital data will be lost are missing.

Finally, there is little research on regional differences in digital heritage protection. Regions in Ukraine present different development levels of infrastructure, financial capability and conflict exposure, which calls for differentiated approaches. There is a gap in current literature about how predictive technologies can be adapted to these different local contexts.

In this study, therefore, it is intended to contribute in the intersection of economy and information technology by solving these unresolved aspects. The proposed analysis not only shows how predictive technologies can be used to predict risks, but also assesses their economic viability under financially and institutionally constrained circumstances. In so doing, the work bridges a key gap between technological innovation and economic decision-making by offering new perspectives for both academic discourse and policy development.

Formulation of the article's objectives.

The main aim of the article is to analyze the possibility of effective use of information technologies for foreseeing and countering the threats of digital heritage loss in Ukraine, especially regarding its economic dimension. This goal can only be attained by establishing the primary factors that lead to the vulnerability of digital heritage, the potential of risk management using predictive technologies and their cost efficiency under financial and institutional limitations.

The study also aims to determine the degree to which macroeconomic volatility, wartime disruption and local variances affect the sustainability of digital preservation systems. Through this, it seeks to shed light on how predictive information technologies can be tailored to the specific needs of Ukrainian institutions and used to increase resilience and protect cultural, scientific, and historical assets.

According to these goals, the research considers the following specific tasks:

1. To identify and categorise the main risk factors impacting upon digital heritage loss in Ukraine (technological, economic and organisational).

2. To find the economic drivers of digital preservation activity, particularly in regards to budgetary allocation, resource limitations, and macroeconomic factors.

3. To assess the impact of predictive information technologies - including artificial intelligence and machine learning - on risk forecasting and vulnerability mitigation

4. In order to create scenario-based model to predict the likelihood of a digital heritage loss under various economic and investment assumptions.

5. To develop practical recommendations to policy makers and institutions about the best way to integrate predictive technologies into national and institutional digital preservation strategies.

The specification of these objectives reflects the urgency of the nature of threats to digital heritage in Ukraine, as well as the need from a scientific standpoint to combine economic analysis with the study of technological solutions for preservation. By accomplishing these goals, the article will, on the one hand, contribute to the academic discourse in the areas of digital economy and risk management, while on the other, offering guidance for practitioners and decision-makers in charge of safeguarding national cultural and scientific patrimony.

Presentation of the main research material. The conducted study revealed a number of patterns related to the risks of loss of digital heritage in Ukraine, and the role of information technologies in predicting and mitigating such risks. The results were organized according to three inter-related dimensions: the economic environment of digital heritage management, the technological readiness of Ukrainian institutions and the efficiency of predictive risk models based on available data. This section summarizes the results of the empirical findings, interprets the economic significance and backs it up with descriptive and econometric evidence.

The purpose of the model is to quantify how institutional resources (IT investment share and staff training), technological risks (frequency of cyberattacks),

and macroeconomic conditions (GDP growth and inflation) influence the probability of digital heritage loss in Ukrainian institutions. Because the dependent variable is binary, logistic regression was chosen, supplemented with robustness checks and scenario forecasting.

Let $Loss_{it} \in \{0,1\}$ denote whether institution iii at time ttt experienced digital data loss. Then:

$$\Pr(Loss_{it} = 1) = \Lambda(\eta_{it}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\eta_{it})} \quad (1)$$

$$\eta_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ITShare_{it} + \beta_2 Training_{it} + \beta_3 Cyber_{it} + \beta_4 GDP_t + \beta_5 Infl_t + \gamma^T X_{it} + \mu_i + \tau_t \quad (2)$$

Expected signs:

$$\beta_1 < 0, \beta_2 < 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 < 0, \beta_5 > 0.$$

where

- $Loss_{it}$ - Equals 1 if a digital loss/disruption event occurred, 0 otherwise.
- $ITShare_{it}$ - Share of IT investment in the institution's budget; higher shares reduce risk.
- $Training_{it}$ - Share of staff trained in digital preservation; expected to lower probability of errors.
- $Cyber_{it}$ - Frequency of cyberattacks or major incidents; raises risk of loss.
- GDP_t - Ukraine's GDP growth rate; higher growth is associated with reduced vulnerability.
- $Infl_t$ - Inflation rate; resource stress that increases risks.
- X_{it} - Control variables (institution size, type, backup frequency, cloud storage use, etc.).
- μ_i, τ_t - Institution and time fixed effects to capture unobserved heterogeneity.
- α - intercept, baseline risk when all predictors are zero.

- β_1 - effect of IT investment share (expected negative).
- β_2 - effect of staff training (expected negative).
- β_3 - effect of cyberattack frequency (expected positive).
- β_4 - effect of GDP growth (expected negative).
- β_5 - effect of inflation (expected positive).
- γ^T - vector of coefficients for control variables (institution type, size, backup use, etc.).

Results from the logit model (2022 - 2024 sample) indicate:

- IT investments:
 $\hat{\beta}_1 \approx -0.47$ ($p < 0.05$). A +1 percentage point increase in IT share reduces risk by ≈ 0.6 p.p.
- Staff training:
 $\hat{\beta}_2 \approx -0.29$ ($p < 0.05$). Expanding training by 10 p.p. lowers risk by $\approx 2-3$ p.p.
- Cyberattacks:
 $\hat{\beta}_3 \approx 0.61$ ($p < 0.05$). Each additional serious attack increases risk by $\approx 1-2$ p.p.
- GDP growth:
 $\hat{\beta}_4 \approx -0.81$ ($p < 0.01$). +1% GDP growth reduces risk by $\approx 0.8-0.9$ p.p.
- Inflation:
 $\hat{\beta}_5 \approx 0.32$ ($p < 0.05$). +1% inflation increases risk by ≈ 0.3 p.p.

Predictive quality:

AUC $\approx 0.80-0.83$, pseudo- $R^2 \approx 0.40$. Robust to probit/cloglog specifications and controls.

Scenario forecasts (2025–2030):

- 1) Pessimistic: ITShare 5–6%, GDP –1% $\rightarrow \approx 49\%$ probability of large-scale loss.
- 2) Baseline: ITShare 7%, GDP +2% $\rightarrow \approx 32\%$.
- 3) Optimistic: ITShare 12–13%, GDP +3.5%, expanded training $\rightarrow \approx 18\%$.

Conclusions from the model:

1. Increasing the share of IT investment and staff training substantially lowers risks of digital heritage loss.
2. Frequent cyberattacks significantly increase risk, making cybersecurity and monitoring critical.
3. Macroeconomic conditions strongly affect resilience; during downturns and inflation spikes, supplementary financial mechanisms are needed.
4. Combining econometric modeling with scenario forecasting provides actionable guidance for institutions and policymakers: to target $\geq 10\text{--}12\%$ of budgets for IT preservation, expand training coverage, and implement coordinated national strategies.

The preliminary analysis showed that Ukraine's digital heritage landscape is under pressure from external shocks such as war-related threats, cyberattacks and infrastructural disruptions as well as internal limitations associated with underinvestment in technological infrastructure and lack of institutional coordination. Survey data received from cultural, academic, and archival institutions corroborated the highest risk factors for digital heritage loss, which are associated with financial instability (34%), technologies that are becoming obsolete (28%) and cybersecurity threats (21%), while human resources deficits (17%) are significant but secondary. Such proportions are consistent with the economics of the situation in which resource-allocation is highly constrained, and priority is often accorded to immediate recovery over long-term digital preservation.

Table 1

Main risk factors for digital heritage loss in Ukraine (2024 data, % of respondents)

Risk factor	Share of respondents (%)
Financial instability	34
Technological obsolescence	28

Cybersecurity threats	21
Human resource deficits	17

Source: authors development using data from [17-40].

The study of budgetary allocations showed that Ukrainian institutions spend an average of 5 - 7% of annual operational expenses on information technologies for preservation and risk management. This is lower than the European average of 12-15%, which reflects an economic imbalance, which results in greater vulnerability. Despite the limited resources, it can be observed that institutions that spend more than 10% of their operational budget on IT infrastructure show a much reduced probability of incidents with data loss, indicating a strong positive link between technological investment and risk resilience.

This relationship was confirmed by econometric modeling. A regression analysis performed based on data from 42 institutions indicated that each 1% increase in the share of IT investment is associated with a 0.6 percentage point lower probability of digital heritage loss ($p < 0.05$). The elasticity coefficient of -0.47 showed that the effect was economically important, even if moderate in absolute value. This suggests that marginal increases in investment lead to meaningful improvements in protection, but lack of both complementary measures such as staff training and cybersecurity strategies.

In addition to institutional investment, macroeconomic conditions determine the risks of digital heritage loss. Periods of GDP contraction and spikes in inflation in Ukraine were found to correlate to lower institutional allocations for digital preservation. Specifically, the years 2022-2023, characterized by the contraction in the war and the financial stress, saw a 23% decline in new IT infrastructure projects in the cultural and educational institutions. The econometric analysis further showed that during a 1% decrease in GDP growth the predicted chance of digital heritage loss incidents rose by 0.8 percentage points, highlighting the sensitivity of digital preservation efforts to economic shocks.

Table 2

Economic and institutional determinants of digital heritage loss risks (logit model results)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	Significance (p-value)
IT investment share in budget (%)	-0.47	0.12	0.018
GDP growth rate (%)	-0.81	0.26	0.004
Inflation rate (%)	0.32	0.09	0.021
Staff trained in IT preservation (%)	-0.29	0.14	0.044
Cyberattack frequency (per year)	0.61	0.20	0.011
Constant	2.04	0.38	0.000

Source: authors development using data from [17-40].

The role of cybersecurity emerged as particularly critical. Ukraine has experienced a sharp increase in cyberattacks since 2022, with many directed at government databases, university repositories, and online cultural archives. Institutions reporting more than three cyber incidents annually were found to have a 2.5 times higher risk of permanent data corruption or temporary unavailability, highlighting the compounded impact of technological and geopolitical risks. Predictive models incorporating cyberattack frequency improved explanatory power (pseudo- $R^2 = 0.41$), confirming that the integration of cybersecurity indicators is essential in risk prediction frameworks.

Human resource capacity was another factor influencing outcomes. Institutions where more than 30% of staff had received specialized training in digital preservation demonstrated a 19% lower probability of data loss compared to those with minimal training. However, training programs remain limited in Ukraine, often

donor-funded and sporadic. The absence of systemic government-backed initiatives reduces the scalability of human capital development. This limitation was reflected in the econometric model, where staff training showed significance but weaker effect size compared to IT investment and macroeconomic indicators.

In addition to regression-based evidence, scenario simulations were conducted to estimate potential future risks under different economic and investment assumptions. Under a baseline scenario (continuation of current investment levels and moderate economic recovery), the probability of large-scale digital heritage loss was projected at 32% over the next five years. In a pessimistic scenario (continued economic contraction and stagnant IT investment), the probability increased to 49%. Conversely, in an optimistic scenario where institutions increase IT allocations to at least 12% of budgets and implement coordinated national strategies, the probability could be reduced to 18% (Table 3). These simulations illustrate the economic stakes of strategic investment decisions.

Table 3

Scenario-based predictions of digital heritage loss risks in Ukraine (2025-2030)

Scenario	IT investment share (%)	GDP growth trend	Predicted probability of digital heritage loss (%)
Pessimistic	5–6	–1% per year	49
Baseline	7	+2% per year	32
Optimistic	12–13	+3.5% per year	18

Source: authors development using data from [17-40].

Besides institutional and macroeconomic perspectives, the analysis focused on the role of predictive technologies per se. Ukrainian organizations are increasingly using artificial intelligence and machine learning applications in

systems for anomaly detection, backup validation and risk prediction. For example, case studies found that machine learning algorithms using historical incident data increased accuracy of risk prediction by 22% compared to traditional statistical approaches. However, adoption continues to be patchy - only 27% of institutions surveyed said they were actively using predictive IT tools, whilst most had not integrated IT into wider risk management systems. This is a function of not only financial constraints, but also a need for expertise to operationalize advanced tools.

Results indicated that the differences in resilience in institutions with and without predictive IT adoption were clear. Those using predictive algorithms had a low incidence of unplanned data loss (12% vs. 25%) and faster recovery time from disruption (mean downtime 3.2 days vs. 6.8 days) than those who did not. The cost of downtime is indeed considerable: it has been estimated that the cost of each day an institution's digital archive is unavailable ranges from USD 2,500 to USD 5,000, for lost services, reputational damage and recovery. Furthermore, the cost avoidance from predictive IT was equivalent to 1.1-1.7% of the total annual budget at institutions that had implemented predictive IT, highlighting the economic benefit of proactive IT investment.

Finally, the spatial analysis of Ukrainian regions identified the difference levels of risk of digital heritage. Institutions in the central and western region of Ukraine were relatively more resilient due to better funding flows, donor support and more stable infrastructure. Conversely, risks were highest in areas directly impacted by conflict and destruction of infrastructure, where chances of data loss exceeded 50% in some areas of eastern and southern parts of the country. This regional diversity indicates that any national digital preservation policy needs to consider differentiated vulnerabilities and provide them with targeted support to the most fragile regions.

Taken together, the results show that the economic side of digital heritage loss in Ukraine prediction is a complex phenomenon. It is not just dependent on direct

investment in IT infrastructure but also on wider macroeconomic stability, cybersecurity risks, human capital, and regional disparities. The contribution of predictive information technologies is increasing, but their economic utility is limited by uneven adoption and lack of incorporation into institutional strategies. The econometric and scenario-based evidence emphasizes the need for coordinated policies that marry financial mechanisms, capacity building, and technological innovation in order to secure Ukraine's digital heritage within conditions of instability and transformation.

The results of the study enable to formulate a number of recommendations for strengthening institutional practices and national strategies of digital preservation in Ukraine. At the institutional level, heritage, cultural and research institutions should make it a priority to allocate at least ten percent of the operational budgets towards information technologies devoted to preservation and prediction of risks. Alongside the use of financial allocations, institutions must incorporate predictive tools like machine learning-based monitoring, automated backup verification, and integrity checks into their regular workflows. Staff training should be extended so that a minimum of one-third of the personnel are capable of competences in digital preservation, which has a direct impact on reducing such vulnerabilities to data loss.

At the national level, a coordinated digital preservation framework is needed to develop. Such a strategy should involve the establishment of centralized repositories for critical heritage data, the implementation of common standards for metadata and digitization processes, and the creation of a cybersecurity coordination center with a focus on cultural and scientific assets. Financial mechanisms should be introduced to promote investment in predictive technologies such as state subsidies, donor matching funds, and public-private partnerships. Priority should be given to the support of institutions in areas with the highest infrastructural instability and conflict, where threats of digital heritage loss are most acute.

Together, these measures would be part of a resilient system where predictive technologies would be incorporated into not only daily institutional practices but also national policy frameworks to ensure the digital heritage is not only protected through technological innovation but also by sustainable economic planning and coordinated governance.

Conclusions. The study confirmed that preservation of digital heritage in Ukraine is exposed to numerous risk factors, mainly financial instability, technological obsolescence, cyber threats and inadequate human resource capacity. The results showed that the institutions that received more allocations of financial resources for information technologies strongly mitigated their vulnerability to the loss of digital heritage, whereas those that were working with limited budgets were exposed to greater risks. The results also showed that macroeconomic instability and disruptions during wars have a measurable impact on the sustainability of digital preservation systems, indicating the sensitivity of digital heritage to broader economic disruptions.

A main finding is that predictive information technologies, if also embedded into institutional strategies, can significantly enhance the capacity to anticipate risks and reduce possible losses. The use of machine learning and other advanced tools was found to improve the accuracy of risk forecasting and save on the costs of unplanned disruptions. However, adoption is also fragmented and uneven, especially for those across regions, directly exposed to conflict or economic stress. This brings out the importance of developing coordinated national strategies to ensure the availability and economic viability of predictive technologies to variously-capable institutions.

The research objectives that were outlined at the beginning of the research have largely been achieved. The significant risks have been identified, the economic determinants of risks analysed and also the role of predictive technologies in risk forecasting has been evaluated. Scenario-based models gave evidence of the effect

of varying degrees of IT investment and economic growth on the likelihood of digital heritage loss. Finally, recommendations were formulated towards policymakers and institutions on how to better integrate predictive technologies into preservation strategies.

At the same time, there are certain facets that need to be studied more. These include the long-term cost-benefit analysis of predictive technologies under changing economic conditions, the potential role of international cooperation in financing digital preservation efforts and the development of region-specific models to address disparities across Ukraine. Addressing these issues will contribute to a better scientific understanding of the protection of the digital heritage and improve the existing practical tools for the protection of cultural and scientific heritage.

To sum up, the given study highlights the fact that the preservation of digital heritage in Ukraine is not only a technological challenge but also an economic one. Balancing scarce resources with the pressing need for assured protection requires an integrated approach, involving a combination of predictive information technologies, rational economic planning and co-ordinated institutional and governmental action.

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